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Pattern of Bacterial Culture in Intensive Care Unit of Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi

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Abstract

Background: Bacterial infections and related sepsis are very common in non-cardiac Intensive Care Units in the healthcare setup of Pakistan. They are one of the leading causes of death in ICUs. This study was conducted to determine the frequency of culture positive patients admitted to ICU of Holy Family Hospital according to age, gender, most common bacterial isolates cultured from different infection sites and their antibiotic sensitivity pattern.

Methods: In this descriptive cross-sectional study, 352 indoor ICU patients' data was taken from records of the ICU of Holy Family Hospital from the year 2009 to 2016. Collected data included the information regarding the site from where the sample was taken, culture positive microbes, and the antibiotic sensitivity of the bacterial isolates.

Results: Over a period from year 2009 to 2016, cultures of 352 patients were included amongst whom 174 (49.4%) were males and 178 (50.6%) were females. 257 (73.0%) were culture positive while 95 (26.9%) showed no growth for any organism. Most frequently isolated organism was *E. coli* 90 (25.6%) followed by *Pseudomonas* 47 (13.4%), Methicillin Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) 38 (10.8%), *Klebsiella* 38 (10.8%), Coliform 14 (4.0%), *Acinetobacter* 12 (3.4%), *Enterobacter* 6 (1.7%), *Providencia* 6 (1.7%) and Methicillin Resistant *Staphylococcus epidermidis* (MRSE) 6 (1.7%). Antibiotic sensitivity of the isolates showed that the predominant bacteria like *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*), *Pseudomonas* and MRSA were most sensitive to Amikacin 39 (43.3%), Polymyxin B 19 (40%) and Vancomycin 23 (73.7%) respectively.

Conclusion: The most common bacteria isolated were *E. coli*, *Pseudomonas*, *Klebsiella*, and MRSA

showing sensitivity to Imipenem, Polymyxin B, SCF and Vancomycin.

Keywords: Bacteria, microbiology, pathogen, Intensive Care Unit, Antibiotic, sensitivity.

Introduction

Infection is a common problem for intensive care unit (ICU) patients and is related to significant mortality and morbidity among patients admitted to the ICUs. Disease and related sepsis are the main source of death in non-cardiovascular ICUs where the death rate is around 60% and it contributes for roughly 40% of ICU expenditures.¹ The overall occurrence rate is 23.7 infections per 1000 patient these days. Nosocomial infections' rates range from 5% to 30% in ICU patients. In spite of the fact that, ICUs in-general include < 5% of all the beds in a hospital, they represent 20% to 25% of all nosocomial infections.² ICU is one of the important sources for hospital acquired infections even in nations where extensive disease prevention and control measures are routinely actualized. The global investigation of infections in ICU done in 2007 included 1265 ICUs from 75 nations, showed that patients who had longer ICU stays had higher rates of infections, particularly infections because of resistant *Staphylococci*, *Acinetobacter*, *Pseudomonas* species, and *Candida* species. Besides, the ICU mortality of contaminated patients was more than twice that of non-infected patients.³ Resistance of ICU related infections to antimicrobial drugs is increasing around the world. This is because of the abuse of antimicrobial agents, immune compromised condition of patients and exogenous transmission of microbes, mostly by hospital personnel.⁴

As almost everything in this universe is undergoing evolution, the microbes causing different ailments are also showing many changes. Therefore, there is an

extreme need to continuously study them to observe any evolution in their course and magnitude. Our study attempts to identify the latest pattern and frequency of various microorganisms causing ailments in our local population especially those in ICU who already are in critical condition. Knowledge of an ICU's most common microbial isolates and their antibiotic sensitivity patterns facilitates the most effective empirical antibiotic treatment and it also helps in making decisions to restrict the availability of certain antibiotics.⁵

Effective hospital infection control policy is the most encouraging point in the prevention and control of ICU related infections, including specific monitoring for the most prevalent infections and hand washing. Healthcare professionals' latest education and increasing their awareness regarding these objectives is the main key to success.⁶ Due to the importance of ICU infections, monitoring studies are important to get the necessary data regarding microbial isolates from particular regions of the body and their antibiotic sensitivity. Therefore, this study was conducted to determine the microbial spectrum and their antibiotic sensitivity in I.C.U of Holy Family Hospital, a tertiary care health facility in Rawalpindi, Pakistan.

Patients And Methods

This descriptive cross-sectional study was initiated after formal approval by Institutional Research Forum (IRF) of Rawalpindi Medical College. Permission was taken from the concerned authorities and study was carried out in ICU of Holy Family Hospital (HFH), for the duration of 3 months from June 2016 to August 2016. From records (2009 to 2016) of ICU, data of ICU patients having bacterial infection was included and patients with any infection other than bacterial i.e. viral, fungal and protozoa etc. were excluded. Anticipated population proportion is 0.6468%.⁹ Keeping level of confidence 95% and absolute precision 0.05%, minimally required sample size calculated through WHO sample size calculator was 352. All the 352 patients from the records were included using simple random sampling technique. A structured pro-forma was designed where information regarding patient's brief history, the site from where the sample was taken, culture results, and the antibiotic sensitivity of the bacterial isolates, extracted from records was noted. Statistical Package of Social Sciences (Version-22) for windows was used for the entry and analysis where descriptive statistics like percentages, frequencies were calculated.

Results

352 patients admitted in I.C.U of Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi, from 2009 to 2016 were included. Amongst all patients, 174 (49.4%) were males and 178 (50.6%) were females with minimum and maximum ages being 12 and 86 years respectively.

Mean age of patients was 36.72 ± 14.95 years. Out of 352 samples 257 (73.0%) were culture positive and the remaining 95 (26.9%) showed no growth for any organism. Amongst the male patients, 126 (72.4%) showed positive cultures while in female patients 131 (73.6%) patients were culture positive. When patients were categorized based on ages up to 35 years and above 35 years, majority of patients belonged to later group i.e. above 35 years and had positive cultures, 122 (77.7%) compared to former group in which 135 (69.2%) were culture positive. The distribution of culture findings are displayed in Table I.

Most frequently isolated organism was *E. coli* 90 (25.6%) followed by *Pseudomonas* 47 (13.4%), MRSA 38 (10.8%) and *Klebsiella* 38 (10.8%). Coliform, *Acinetobacter*, *Enterobacter*, *Providencia* and Methicillin Resistant *Staphylococcus Epidermidis* (MRSE) were less frequent.

E. coli, *Pseudomonas*, *Klebsiella* and MRSA were again the most common microbes observed in all categories of ages and gender. *E. coli* was equal in proportion in males and females (25.3% vs. 25.3%) however it's proportion was slightly higher in patients above 35 years of age compared to those up to 35 years in age (33.1% vs 19.5%). *Pseudomonas* and MRSA were more common in males compared to females who had more cultures of *Klebsiella* compared to males. However in patients up to 35 years of age, *Pseudomonas* and MRSA were more common as compared to *Klebsiella*.

The most common infection sites from which specimens were collected were: Trachea (ETT tip) 90 (25.6%), Urine 88 (25.0%), Trachea (suction catheter tip) 71 (20.2%) and Blood 67 (19.0%), (Figure I). Amongst male patients most common sites were Trachea ETT tip, Urine and Blood (29.3%, 25.9% and 17.8% respectively), whereas in females the commonest sites were Trachea (suction catheter tip), Urine and Blood (24.2%, 24.2% and 20.2%). Amongst patients up to 35 years of ages, the commonest sites for culture sampling were Trachea (ETT tip) and Trachea (suction catheter tip) and urine (30.3%, 22.6% and 19% respectively). In patients above 35 years of age, Blood, Trachea (suction catheter tip) and Trachea (ETT tip) were the commonest sites with percentages of 19.7%, 19.7% and 17.2% respectively.

Antibiotic sensitivity of the isolates showed that the predominant bacteria like E. coli, Pseudomonas, Klebsiella and MRSA were most sensitive to Amikacin 59 (49.9%), Polymyxin-B 19(40%), Cefoparazone+Sulbactam (CFP+SUL) 19(50%) and Vancomycin 23(73.7%) respectively (Table II).

FIGURE I SHOWING SITES FROM WHERE SAMPLES WERE COLLECTED

Table-I Findings Of Culture Test

CULTURE FINDINGS	TOTAL F (%)	MALES F (%)	FEMALES F (%)	AGES UPTO 35 YEARS F (%)	AGES ABOVE 35 YEARS F (%)
Negative(no growth)	95 (27.0%)	48 (27.6%)	47 (26.4%)	60 (30.8%)	35 (22.3%)
E. coli +ve	90 (25.6%)	44 (25.3%)	46 (25.3%)	38 (19.5%)	52 (33.1%)
Pseudomonas +ve	47 (13.4%)	17 (9.8%)	30 (16.9%)	31 (15.9%)	16 (10.2%)
Klebsiella +ve	38 (10.8%)	27 (15.5%)	11 (6.2%)	15 (7.7%)	23 (14.6%)
MRSA +ve	38 (10.8%)	16 (9.2%)	22 (12.4%)	23 (11.8%)	15 (9.6%)
Coliform +ve	14 (4.0%)	7 (4.0%)	7 (3.9%)	7 (3.6%)	7 (4.5%)
Acinetobacter +ve	12 (3.4%)	5 (2.9%)	7 (3.9%)	10 (5.1%)	2 (1.3%)
Enterobacter +ve	6 (1.7%)	4 (2.3%)	2 (1.1%)	1 (0.5%)	5 (3.2%)
Providencia +ve	6 (1.7%)	4 (2.3%)	2 (1.1%)	4 (2.1%)	2 (1.3%)
MRSE +ve	6 (1.7%)	2 (1.1%)	4 (2.2%)	6 (3.1%)	0 (0%)
Total	352 (100%)	174 (100%)	178 (100%)	195 (100%)	157 (100%)

Antimicrobial Agent	KLEBSIELLA	E.COLI	PSEUDOMONAS	MRSA	ENTEROBACTER	PROVIDENCIA	MRSE	ACINETOBACTER	COLIFORM
Ampicillin	4 (10.5%)	9 (10.0%)	2 (4.3%)	4 (10.5%)	0 (0%)	2 (33.3%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	2 (14.3%)
Amikacin	18 (47.4%)	39 (43.3%)	10 (21.3%)	9 (23.3%)	4 (66.7%)	1 (16.7%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	6 (42.9%)
Gentamycin	2 (5.3%)	10 (11.1%)	8 (17.1%)	6 (15.8%)	2 (33.3%)	1 (16.7%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (14.3%)
Tetracyclin	1 (2.6%)	3 (3.3%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	6 (42.9%)
Ceftazidime	3 (7.9%)	17 (18.9%)	5 (10.6%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.7%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (14.3%)
Ceftriaxone	1 (2.6%)	3 (3.3%)	1 (2.1%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (14.3%)
Imipenem	15 (39.5%)	40 (44.4%)	15 (31.9%)	8 (21.1%)	2 (33.3%)	3 (50.0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (14.3%)
Meropenem	1 (2.6%)	18 (20.0%)	3 (6.4%)	6 (15.8%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (14.3%)
Vancomycin	0 (0%)	1 (1.1%)	2 (4.3%)	28 (73.7%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (14.3%)
Ciprofloxacin	5 (13.2%)	8 (8.9%)	7 (14.9%)	4 (10.5%)	1 (16.7%)	0 (0%)	2 (33.3%)	2 (16.7%)	2 (14.3%)
Sparfloxacin	3 (7.9%)	13 (14.4%)	2 (4.3%)	6 (15.8%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (14.3%)
F/NTI	3 (7.9%)	6 (6.7%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	4 (28.6%)
Polymyxin B	10 (26.3%)	19 (21.1%)	19 (40.4%)	5 (13.2%)	2 (33.3%)	3 (50.0%)	0 (0%)	12 (100%)	2 (14.3%)
Aztreonam	1 (2.6%)	5 (5.6%)	1 (2.1%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (14.3%)
Ofloxacin	0 (0%)	2 (2.2%)	7 (14.9%)	2 (5.3%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.7%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (14.3%)
Enoxacin	0 (0%)	2 (2.2%)	0 (0%)	1 (2.6%)	1 (16.7%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (14.3%)
Levofloxacin	8 (21.1%)	12 (13.3%)	18 (38.3%)	6 (15.8%)	2 (33.3%)	3 (50.0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (14.3%)
Fosfomycin	4 (10.5%)	10 (11.1%)	8 (17.0%)	2 (5.3%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	2 (14.3%)
CFP+SUL	19 (50.0%)	26 (28.9%)	9 (19.1%)	2 (5.3%)	3 (50.0%)	1 (16.7%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (14.3%)
Linezolid	0 (0%)	2 (2.2%)	0 (0%)	9 (23.7%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	4 (66.7%)	0 (0%)	2 (14.3%)
Cefaclor	0 (0%)	5 (5.6%)	1 (2.1%)	7 (18.4%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (14.3%)
Cefotaxime	3 (7.9%)	2 (2.2%)	7 (14.9%)	4 (10.5%)	0 (0%)	2 (33.3%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	2 (14.3%)
PIP+TAZ	8 (21.1%)	13 (14.4%)	7 (14.9%)	2 (5.3%)	1 (16.7%)	1 (16.7%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	5 (35.7%)
Polymyxin B	5 (13.2%)	6 (6.7%)	7 (14.9%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	3 (25.0%)	4 (28.6%)

Discussion:

Clinically, antibiotic resistance is a worldwide emerging problem in intensive care units (ICUs).¹⁰ Gram-positive bacteria and Gram-negative bacteria which are antibiotic resistant are reported as major cause of acquired infections in the setup of ICUs.¹⁰ The uncontrolled frequent dependency on broad-spectrum antibiotic drugs is an important cause that ICUs are facing increasing spread and emergence of antibiotic

resistant strains of bacteria.^{10,11} Unnecessary long-term use of anti-bacterial drugs also leads to proliferation and emergence of bacterial strains resistant to antibiotics.^{11,12} Acquired infection prevalence in ICUs is between 12% to 45% so it's of great significance to find the major strains of bacteria developing resistance against antibiotics rendering the infection treatment more difficult.¹³⁻¹⁷

In this study, *E. coli* had the highest frequency (90%), followed by *Pseudomonas* (13.4%), *Klebsiella* (10.8%), and MRSA (10.8%) which are similar to another research conducted in Pakistan.⁷ This indicates that these bacteria are still predominant in ICUs of our country.⁷ In another study conducted in India, *Klebsiella* was the most common isolate (28.57%).⁸ Out of 352 specimens, organisms were isolated in 73% (n=257) and 27% (n=95) cultures were negative whereas in another study conducted in Indonesia, 64.68% (n=249) cultures were positive and 35.32% (n=136) cultures were negative.⁹ This shows that the frequency of positive cultures is higher in our setup.

Regarding the gender distribution in this study, out of 352 samples 257 (73.0%) were culture positive and the remaining 95 (26.9%) showed no growth for any organism. Out of 257 (73.0%) positive cultures 174 (49.4%) were males and 178 (50.5%) were females but if we see the results of a study conducted in India, 27 (69.3%) males and 12 (30.7%) females were affected out of 39 positively cultured patients included in the study.⁸

According to the site of specimen collection, this study showed a higher percentage of specimens were collected from Urinary tract (25%) and blood (19%) as compared to the one done in Indonesia, which showed Urinary Tract frequency to be 7.6% and Blood frequency 3.8%.⁹ However lesser number of specimens were collected from ascitic fluid (0.9%) and respiratory tract (45.6%) comparatively. But the highest number of culture specimens were collected from respiratory tract in both of the studies.⁹ *Klebsiella* showed highest sensitivity to Cefoparazone+Sulbactam (CFP+SUL) (50.0%) and Amikacin (47.4%). *E. coli* had the most sensitivity for Imipenem (44.4%). *Pseudomonas* and *Acinetobacter* showed most sensitivity to Polymyxin B (40.4% and 100% respectively). MRSA was found to be most responsive to Vancomycin (73.7%). *Enterobacter* was most responsive to Amikacin (66.7%). *Providencia* responded best to Imipenem (50.0%) and Levofloxacin (50.05%). Comparison of sensitivity of MRSA to Vancomycin has shown a fall from 100% to 73.7%.⁷

Conclusion

The most common bacteria isolated in ICU were *E. coli*, *Pseudomonas*, *Klebsiella* and MRSA showing higher sensitivity to Amikacin, Polymyxin-B, Cefoparazone+Sulbactam (CFP+SUL) and Vancomycin as compared to other antimicrobial agents.

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